

NATURAL FREQUENCY OF BI-STABLE COMPOSITE PLATES IN THERMAL ENVIRONMENTS

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ABSTRACT

The natural frequency of bi-stable cross-ply $[0_n/90_n]_T$ composite plates under thermomechanical loading is analysed theoretically. Based on Hamilton's principle, in conjunction with the Rayleigh-Ritz method, the analytical model with only 17 unknown terms is applied to predict the natural frequency of bi-stable composite plates. The properties of the composite material in current study are considered to be functions of temperature. The plate is subjected to two different thermal load, i.e. the uniform temperature field and through-thickness thermal gradient. The influence of this two temperature field on the natural frequency of the thin composite plates is predicted theoretically. Moreover, the predicted results are greatly affected by the uncertainty of uncertainties in geometry, material properties and the operating environment. The considered uncertainties include Young's moduli, Poisson's ratio and shear modulus, thermal expansion coefficients, ply thickness, density, cure and ambient temperature. The thermal effect and sensitivity to uncertainties are of great importance to the design and application of morphing structures manufactured from bi-stable composite plates.

THEORETICAL AND NUMERICAL METHODOLOGY

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: Material properties at room temperature and variation with temperature.

Material property	Value in T=20°C	Value with variation in temperature
Longitudinal Young's modulus, E_{11} (Pa)	1.4598×10^{11}	$5 \times 10^5 T^2 + 1.9 \times 10^7 T + 1.454 \times 10^{11}$
Transverse Young's modulus, E_{22} (Pa)	1.176×10^{10}	$1.2 \times 10^6 T^2 - 1.76 \times 10^8 T + 1.48 \times 10^{10}$
Poisson's ratio, ν_{12}	0.3091	$4 \times 10^{-7} T^2 - 1.04 \times 10^{-3} T + 0.3297$
Shear modulus, G_{12} (Pa)	6.972×10^9	$-3 \times 10^4 T^2 - 7.3 \times 10^6 T + 7.13 \times 10^9$
Longitudinal thermal expansion coefficient, α_{11} ($^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$)	2.64×10^{-6}	$10^{-11} T^3 + 6 \times 10^{-10} T^2 - 1.88 \times 10^{-7} T + 6.08 \times 10^{-6}$
Transverse thermal expansion coefficient, α_{22} ($^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$)	2.65×10^{-5}	2.65×10^{-5}
Density ρ (kg/m^3)	1600	1600

Table 2: Maximum change in natural frequency for a $\pm 10\%$ variation in each design variable.

Variable	Configuration (%)		Frequency (%)	
	-10%	+10%	-10%	+10%
E_{11} (Pa)	4.63	-4.33	-2.79	2.70
E_{22} (Pa)	-4.68	4.10	-2.24	2.17
ν_{12}	0.643	-0.649	-0.094	0.101
G_{12} (Pa)	-0.117	0.101	-0.049	0.051
α_{11} ($^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$)	1.22	-1.22	-0.048	0.048
α_{22} ($^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$)	-12.2	12.3	0.488	-0.472
t (mm)	13.4	-10.8	-10.62	10.68
$T - T_0$ ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	-11.0	11.0	0.439	-0.426
ρ (kg/m^3)	—	—	5.41	4.65

Table 3: Maximum change in natural frequency for a $\pm 10\%$ change in temperature change

Variable temperature	Configuration (%)		Frequency (%)	
	-10%	+10%	-10%	+10%
Temperature change only	-11.0	11.0	0.439	-0.426
All	-9.33	4.55	-3.16	4.39
E_{11} (Pa)	-11.2	11.2	0.581	-0.519
E_{22} (Pa)	-17.3	19.6	-2.94	3.80
ν_{12}	-10.7	10.7	0.388	-0.373
G_{12} (Pa)	-11.0	9.33	0.428	-0.417
α_{11} ($^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$)	-2.35	-2.68	0.094	0.107

CONCLUSIONS AND REFERENCES

- Both of the uniform temperature field and through-thickness thermal gradients have a significant effect on natural frequency of bi-stable cross-ply composite plates
- The influence of temperature dependence characteristic cannot be ignored on natural frequency of the bi-stable plate
- Special care should be taken in characterizing these critical parameters to minimize the uncertainties and improve confidence in the model prediction
- Wu, Z., Li, H., and Friswell, M., Advanced nonlinear dynamic modelling of bi-stable composite plates, Composite Structures, 201, 2018, pp. 582-596 (doi: 10.1016/j.compstruct.2018.06.072).